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Upskilling workers of SMEs with low Digital intensity

Project Newsletter

Newsletter #4 - May 2026

Learning Experiences Catalogue

The USMED consortium has completed the development of more than 60 Open Educational Resources designed to support digital upskilling in the Accommodation and Food sector.

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Tailored Learning Pathways

USMED is developing structured learning pathways to help workers, learners, trainers, and SMEs strengthen digital competences according to specific needs and proficiency levels.

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Next Steps: Digital Infrastructure Development

The consortium is progressing with the development of the USMED digital infrastructure, which will host the Learning Experiences Catalogue, tailored pathways, and tools for the recognition of learning outcomes.

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OUR LEARNING EXPERIENCES CATALOGUE IS READY

The consortium has completed the development of the Learning Experiences Catalogue, a key project result designed to support digital skills development in the Accommodation and Food sector. The Catalogue responds to the digital competence needs identified through the project's research activities and the **Digital Skills Assessment Tool**. It provides practical, accessible, and reusable learning resources for workers, learners, trainers, VET providers, and SME managers operating in contexts of low digital intensity.

Catalogue Composition

The Catalogue includes **62 Open Educational Resources (OERs)**, organised as modular micro-learning units and focused on digital topics relevant to the sector. These include areas such as: artificial intelligence; e-commerce; cloud-based tools; management software; cybersecurity; digital communication; online reputation; data management; social media and digital marketing.

The Catalogue has been developed through a coordinated process involving consortium partners and external contributors:

- **35 OERs developed by project partners:** Each consortium partner contributed five original resources, developed in English and in the relevant national language of the partnership.
- **15 OERs identified from European project results:** The Digital Economy Lab of the University of Warsaw supported the identification of existing relevant resources from the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform and other European initiatives, contributing to the reuse and visibility of previously developed educational materials.
- **12 OERs collected through an Open Call:** Additional resources were submitted by vocational education and training stakeholders, supporting the project's objective of creating an open and collaborative ecosystem for digital learning in the sector.

CREATING TAILORED LEARNING PATHWAYS

USMED is developing Tailored Learning Pathways that connect selected OERs according to learners' needs, professional profiles, and digital competence levels. These pathways are designed to support workers, learners, trainers, and SME representatives in addressing specific digital skills gaps identified through the Digital Skills Assessment Tool. The pathways provide curated sequences of learning experiences that facilitate targeted and progressive upskilling.

Six Learning Pathways

We have structured six tailored learning pathways, divided into three proficiency levels:

- 2 **Foundation** pathways
- 2 **Intermediate** pathways
- 2 **Advanced** pathways

Each pathway combines **a minimum of 10 Open Educational Resources**, sequenced to support coherent progression and practical skills development. This structure enables learners and training professionals to focus on the competences most relevant to their starting point and objectives.

A Pedagogical Model Based on Practical Learning

The development of the Learning Experiences Catalogue follows the ADDIE instructional design model - Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation - to ensure that resources are coherent, learner-centred, and aligned with real training needs.

The project's methodological approach places emphasis on practical application and workplace relevance, modular and reusable content, interactive learning elements, clear learning objectives, activities that encourage reflection and application, accessibility and inclusive design.

The Catalogue includes formats such as **interactive modules, videos, case studies, practical exercises, branching scenarios, simulations**, and **digital learning activities** aimed at promoting engagement and transferability to work contexts.

NEXT STEPS: DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT UNDERWAY

Following the development of the Learning Experiences Catalogue and the Pathways, USMED is advancing the next phase of work: the development of its Digital Infrastructure.

Three Interconnected Digital Tools

1. eLearning Platform - The platform will host the Learning Experiences Catalogue, Open Educational Resources, and Tailored Learning Pathways. It will support hybrid and virtual VET delivery, provide multilingual access, and connect assessment results with relevant training options.

2. OER Registration Tool - This tool will allow IVET and CVET providers to submit additional Open Educational Resources for possible inclusion in the Catalogue. Submissions will be reviewed for quality, relevance, and alignment with the project methodology, helping keep the Catalogue updated over time.

3. Europass Digital Credentials Support Tool - The EDC Support Tool will help VET providers generate and issue Europass Digital Credentials linked to completed learning experiences. It will be aligned with relevant European standards and supported by a dedicated implementation guidebook.

Once the infrastructure reaches the pilot stage, the consortium will involve at least 175 early adopters, including vocational teachers, trainers and learners.

Stay informed!

Further information on the pilot phase and opportunities for stakeholder participation will be shared through the project website and communication channels.

Interested in collaborating with the consortium or learning more about USMED?

[Contact Us](#)

external link to the project website

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